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Spectrophotometric Determination of Tetramethylene Thiram Disulphide (Thiram) by Extraction of its Molybdenum Complex

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THIRAM sulphides are conveniently determined on the basis of the decomposition of this type of compounds by hot mineral acid to the amine and carbon disulphide. The amount of either of these hydrolysis products can be determined either iodometrically¹ or colorimetrically^{2,3}. Thiram mono- and disulphides may be determined if a digestion with sodium bisulphide is employed prior to the distillation from acid solution of the carbon disulphide⁴. Thiram could be titrated with copper sulphate in presence of hydroquinone⁵. Thiram is determined in grains by colorimetric method by cuprous chloride⁶. But these are all time-consuming processes. It is considered of interest to determine thiram by a simple, direct and rapid spectrophotometric method.

Accordingly, we present here a sensitive and selective method for the spectrophotometric determination of thiram after extracting its molybdenum complex into isobutyl methyl ketone.

Experimental

A Spectronic 20 colorimeter was used for recording absorption measurements. Purity of thiram (Wilson Laboratories) was checked by elemental analysis and m.p. A 0.1% solution of thiram was prepared in 0.1N NaOH solution and boiled for 20 min, cooled, filtered and standardised³ and further diluted as desired with distilled water. A 2% (w/v) sodium molybdate (pure, E. Merck) solution was prepared in distilled water. Stock solutions of other elements were prepared by dissolving suitable salts in water or NaOH solution. Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing solutions of the elements to give the required composition.

Procedure: To an aliquot containing 400 μg of thiram was added 2M H_2SO_4 (0.5 ml) and 2% sodium molybdate (1.5 ml) and the final volume was made to 5 ml with distilled water. The aqueous solution was shaken with isobutyl methyl ketone (5 ml) for 1 min. The two phases were allowed to separate and the organic phase was transferred into a dry tube containing anhydrous calcium chloride. Extract with

another 5 ml of isobutyl methyl ketone from the aqueous phase gave negligible absorbance indicating the complete extraction in the first step itself. A portion of the dried solution (first step) was taken and its absorbance was measured at 420 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of thiram-molybdenum complex in isobutyl methyl ketone was recorded against reagent blank. The complex absorbed strongly at 420 nm. The absorbance of the extract increased with the addition of upto 0.5 ml of 2M H_2SO_4 , but decreased with further addition. The absorbance of the extract remained constant for 1.0–2.0 ml of 2% sodium molybdate solution. Of all the solvents studied, this complex is not extractable into benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, toluene and hexane, but is extracted with n-butyl acetate, amyl acetate, diethyl ether, butan-2-one, ethyl acetate, acetyl acetate, isobutyl alcohol and isobutyl methyl ketone. Maximum absorbance was observed with isobutyl methyl ketone and hence used in this method. The absorbance of the complex remained practically constant for more than 2 h indicating that the complex is quite stable in the extract.

Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range of 5.0–110.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of the final solution. The limit of detection is 1.2 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity (for an absorbance of 0.001) were calculated to be $0.156 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.154 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively at 420 nm. Aliquot containing 400 μg of thiram gave mean absorbance of 0.52 with ten replicate readings with relative standard deviation of $\pm 0.515\%$. In Cullen⁸ and Chmiel³ methods, minimum amount of thiram equivalent to 20 μg of CS_2 can be estimated, whereas in the present method, the minimum amount corresponds to 15.72 μg of CS_2 . Although this method is less sensitive than that of Lowen⁷, the minimum amount in this method corresponds to 10 μg of CS_2 , but is preferred because of its selectivity and its application in simultaneous determinations.

The composition of the molybdenum-thiram complex was found to be 1 : 1 i.e. $\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}\text{O}_2$ (TMTD).

Effect of diverse ions: Sample solutions containing 400 μg of thiram and various amounts of different alkali metal salts or metal ions were prepared and the determination of thiram was studied and the general procedure was applied. The following metal ions (μg amount in parentheses) did not interfere in the determination of thiram 400 μg in 5 ml of the final solution: Pb^{II} (504), Bi^{III} (200), Zn^{II} (660), Cd^{II} (84) and Mn^{II} (40). Cu^{II} interfered strongly. But the following ions (mg amount in parenthesis) were tolerated: citrate (20), bromide (40), nitrate (1), chloride (1), oxalate (20), iodide (1), tartarate (10), thiosulphate (0.5), thiocyanate (0.5), EDTA (0.6), sulphide (0.5) and sulphite (0.6). Sodium orthophosphate interfered strongly.

Determination of thiram (tetramethylene thiuram disulphide), in presence of zineb (zinc bis ethylene dithiocarbamate), maneb (manganese bis ethylene dithiocarbamate), nabam (disodium bis ethylene dithiocarbamate), vapam (sodium monomethyl dithiocarbamate), ziram (zinc dimethyl dithiocarbamate) and ferbam (ferric dimethyl dithiocarbamate): Interference of some of the common reagents like zineb, maneb, nabam, vapam, ferbam and ziram which are mostly used as pesticides has been studied. Nabam, zineb, maneb and vapam formed blue coloured complexes in the aqueous phase which were extractable into isobutyl methyl ketone, i.e. on boiling only, whereas thiram formed yellow coloured complex which was extractable in isobutyl methyl ketone in cold. The following compounds (mg amounts in parentheses) did not interfere in the determination of thiram (400 µg) in 5 ml of the final solution: nabam (1), zineb (1), maneb (1) and vapam (0.5). Ziram and ferbam, if present, interfered.

Simultaneous determination of thiram and zineb: Synthetic mixtures of thiram and zineb in various proportions were prepared. Taking advantage of the colour of the molybdenum-thiram (yellow) and molybdenum-zineb (blue), thiram and zineb can be determined simultaneously. Binary mixture was dissolved in 0.1N NaOH and boiled to dissolve thiram. To this solution, appropriate amounts of 2M H₂SO₄ and 2% sodium molybdate solution were added, yellow coloured complex formed by thiram with sodium molybdate in cold was extractable into isobutyl methyl ketone whereas blue coloured complex of zineb-molybdenum was not extractable in cold. So aqueous phase was boiled for 5–7 min, then cooled and extracted with isobutyl methyl ketone. The absorbance of the extracts were measured at 420 nm for thiram-molybdenum complex and at 670 nm for zineb-molybdenum complex and the amount of thiram and ziram were determined from their respective calibration curves.

Similarly, simultaneous determination of thiram and maneb, thiram and nabam, thiram and vapam were possible (Table 1).

TABLE 1—SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF ZINEB AND THIRAM FROM SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Amount taken (µg)		Amount found (µg)		Error (%)	
Zineb	Thiram	Zineb	Thiram	Zineb	Thiram
20	50	19.75	49.65	-1.25	-0.70
40	100	39.75	99.40	-0.63	-0.60
60	150	59.50	149.0	-0.84	-0.67
80	200	79.50	201.0	-0.63	+0.50

The wide applicability of the method was tested by the satisfactory analysis of a variety of synthetic samples containing thiram upto 400 µg in the aliquot. The method is quite selective for thiram determination in the presence of zineb, maneb, nabam and vapam. The proposed method is quite simple and rapid as it takes less than 15 min for thiram determination after preparation of thiram solution. It is one of the sensitive methods available for thiram

determination and could be used in the analysis of commercial samples and for residual analysis of thiram from various food stuff.

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Extractive Determination of Copper(II) Present in some Biological Samples with Lead Salt of Dipropylthiocarbamate in Chloroform by Standard Addition Method

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It is evident from the literature that no work on the extraction of copper(II) with dipropylthiocarbamate has been reported. The present paper describes a method of extractive estimation of copper(II) from some biological samples by standard addition method using lead dipropylthiocarbamate in chloroform as extractant.

Experimental

Elco pH meter, Spectronic-20 (Bausch and Lomb) and Shimadzu recording spectrophotometer were used. Chemicals used were of A.R. grade, otherwise specified. Commercial grade chloroform was purified¹ and distilled. The fraction collected at 60–81° was used as diluent for the extraction.

To a mixture of potassium nitrate solution (10% ; 5 ml) and lead acetate solution (0.05 g in 10 ml water), was added dipropylthiocarbamate (0.1 g) followed by chloroform (100 ml). The mixture was shaken for 10 min and allowed to equilibrate. The chloroform layer was collected and diluted upto 250 ml with chloroform. Required amount of pentahydrated copper sulphate was dissolved in water and standardised. The desired metal ion concentration was prepared from this solution.